

Research Questionnaire

Delphi Study – Round Two

Project: Heterogeneous Collaboration and Conflict in Spatial Data Co-Production

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Instruction

This second-round Delphi survey questionnaire contains ***five sections***:

- Section A: Personal Information
- Section B: Topic of Conflict
- Section C: Factors Leading to Conflicts
- Section D: Effect of Conflict
- Section E: Potential Conflict Management Method

Please fill out your personal information in Section A, which will only be used for internal identification purpose. ***Sections B to E are based on the results from the first-round Delphi survey*** (Please refer to *Results of First Round Delphi Survey.docx* for more information), ***which asks you how much you agree with each item on Likert scale***. At the end of each section (B, C, D, and E), you could suggest any addition, amendment, and/or removal of an item to the list, as necessary. Your response to this questionnaire will be integrated with other survey participants' responses to reach consensus for each section.

Please kindly return the completed questionnaire by 9 July 2021 to Ms. Youjin Choe via email (ychoe@student.unimelb.edu.au).

Your participation to this research is much appreciated.

Section A: Personal Information

Name	
Age range (please mark "X")	Under 18
	18 to 20
	21 to 30
	31 to 40
	41 to 50
	51 to 60
Affiliation (please mark "X")	Over 60
	Volunteering individual
	Corporation (Please specify:)
	Government agency (Please specify:)
	Non-governmental organisation (Please specify:)
Others (Please specify:)	
Geographic scope of interest (for mapping)	

Section B: Topic of conflict

1. Please indicate how strongly you agree/disagree with the following statements:

Conflicts amongst OSM mappers are attributed to:

		Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)
Production and usage of OSM data	First-round results					
	Tagging					
	Mapping archaeological site					
	Border disputes					
	Vandalism					
	AI-assisted mapping					
	Mechanical edits					
	Organized edits					
	Import					
	Revert					
	Correct form of mapping					
	Desired level of detail					
Effect of mapping						
Data license						
OSM members	Language barrier					
	Gender					
	Craft mappers vs. others					
	Volunteer vs. paid mappers					
	Influence of corporate partners					
	Diversity and inclusion					
OSM governance	Western-centered member activity					
	Communication channel					
	Code of conduct					

OSMF Board					
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2. Would you like to make any additions in Question 1?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

3. Would you like to make any amendments in Question 1?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

4. Are any of the statements from the Question 1 redundant and be removed?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

Section C: Factors Leading to Conflict

5. Please indicate how strongly you agree/disagree with the following statements:

Conflicts amongst OSM mappers happen due to factors such as:

First-round results		Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)
OSM members	Language barrier					
	Different age					
	Different personality					
	Different cultural background					
	Different educational background					
	Different interest, priority, and value					
	Ownership					
Member-to-member interaction	Incompatible personality					
	Uncooperative behaviour					
	Different level of tolerance					
	Negative previous experience					
	"Us vs. them" subgroup					
OSM governance	Different level of access to resources					
	Communication					
	Open, latent and non-hierarchical structure					
External environment	Geopolitics and political economy					

6. Would you like to make any additions in Question 5?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

7. Would you like to make any amendments in Question 5?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

8. Are any of the statements from the Question 5 redundant and be removed?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

Section D: Effect of Conflict

9. Please indicate how strongly you agree/disagree with the following statements:

Effects of conflict on OSM and the mappers include:

First-round results		Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)
OSM data quality	Damaged map					
	Biased representation of real world					
OSM member experience	Discouraging member participation and motivation					
	Lower trust in the community					
	No engagement with other members					
	Members leaving OSM					
	Lack of stable foundation for developers					
	High barrier for new members					
	Navigating different interests and opinions					
OSM data user experience	Damaged OSM's reputation					
	Degraded user experience					
OSM resources	Wasted time					
	Financial cost					
OSM governance	Toxic atmosphere in the community					
	Limited group of members participating in OSM					
	Setting undesirable precedents on local practices					
	Community fragmentation					
	Difficulty in building community consensus					
	Existing mechanisms and institution leading to increased bureaucracy					

10. Would you like to make any additions in Question 9?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

11. Would you like to make any amendments in Question 9?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

12. Are any of the statements from the Question 9 redundant and be removed?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

Section E: Potential Conflict Management Method

13. Please indicate how strongly you agree/disagree with the following statements:

Conflicts amongst OSM mappers can be resolved through:

First-round results		Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)
Mapping	Revert of structural damages					
OSM members	Open communication by corporate partners					
	Matured member interaction					
	Valuation of diverse participations in OSM					
	Shared goal among the members on what OSM is for					
OSM governance	Live member conversation					
	Community survey					
	Improved member negotiation and collaboration process					
	Improved support for members' collaboration experience					
	Training of new members					
	Full-time employees for conflict management					
	Channels for conflict management					
	Enforced code of conduct					
	Structured groupings of members by level of expertise/experience					
	Populating OSM working groups					
	Improved diversity and inclusion					
	Stronger action by OSMF Board					

14. Would you like to make any additions in Question 13?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

15. Would you like to make any amendments in Question 13?

Yes No

If yes, please explain:

16. Are any of the statements from the Question 13 redundant and be removed?

Yes No

If yes, please explain: